

Inhibitive effect of some Schiff base ligands for corrosion of mild steel in acidic media[†]

S. Sanyal* and Anil Kumar

Department of Post Graduate Studies in Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj-816 109, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : sanyalsom@yahoo.co.in, anilkumar_ism@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Schiff bases are widely used in complex formation as organic ligands. The effectiveness of some Schiff bases as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in acid media has been studied by both weight loss and electro-chemical methods. Studies on the effect of inhibitor concentration and temperature on the corrosion of mild steel have been made. The inhibitor appears to function through adsorption following Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The thermodynamic parameters such as activation energy and free energy of adsorption were calculated. With the addition of methyl group in the ligand, +I effect increases, causing increase in the π -electron density on the azomethene group giving increased inhibitive effect. More effective inhibition was found due to increased adsorption caused by greater π -electron cloud when a phenyl group is added to the ligand. The polarization studies show that the inhibitors act as mixed inhibitors blocking both anodic and cathodic sites.

Keywords : Schiff bases, corrosion inhibitors, mild steel, acid media, inhibition mechanism.

Introduction

Corrosion phenomena, their prevention and control have become a perpetual struggle between man and nature, particularly in view of the modern age technological developments and increasing need and use of metallic materials in all facets of technology. This issue has necessitated the increasing interest in research into the environment/metal interface reactions and the means of mitigating the damaging effects of corrosion on metals and alloys.

Mild steel is commercially used in the manufacture of accessories equipments in various projects as it is economical. Corrosion studies are of prime importance because it is encountered in practically all industries like chemical, nuclear plants, thermal power plants, aerospace, hydrospace projects, petroleum refineries etc. The Schiff base transition metal complexes have been extensively studied in recent years¹⁻⁶. Schiff bases also find place in many important fields of interest⁷⁻¹¹. This base and its various substituted derivatives have also been reported to be used as corrosion inhibitors widely¹²⁻²⁷. In the present

work, an attempt has been made to study the inhibitive effect of Schiff base ligands like salicylanilidine-*o*-phenylenediamine acetanilide and its substituted derivatives for corrosion of mild steel in acid media. The general structure of the Schiff base ligands used is given in Fig. 1.

	Name	Abbreviation
H	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamineacetanilide	Salphac
CH ₃	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediaminepropylenilide	Salphro
C ₆ H ₅	Salicylanilidine- <i>o</i> -phenylenediaminemethylbenzanilide	Salphben

Fig. 1. General structure of the Schiff base ligands.

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

Results and discussion*Weight loss studies :*

The effect of concentration of three inhibiting organic ligands – Salphac, Salphro and Salphben on the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ is given in Table 1. The Table shows that all the ligands tested as inhibitor provide de-

increase of surface coverage at higher concentration of the additive which retards dissolution of metal. The electron donating properties of nitrogen atom along with delocalized π -electrons can be attributed for higher inhibition efficiencies.

Thermodynamic parameters were studied to under-

Table 1. Effect of concentration of three inhibitors on the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ at 30 ± 1 °C (duration 1 h)
(Values in parantheses represent percentage inhibition)

Name of inhibitors	Inhibitor conc. (mM)	Wt. loss (mg/dm ² /h)	Surface coverage (θ)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	E_a (kJ/mol)
Blank	-	21.21 (-)	-	3237.23	17.49
Salphac	0.5	10.41 (50.91)	0.5091	1584.24	-
	1.0	9.95 (53.07)	0.5307	1399.21	-
	2.0	8.62 (58.88)	0.5888	1003.27	-
	4.0	4.66 (77.22)	0.7722	999.98	18.72
	8.0	4.49 (78.83)	0.7883	689.96	20.42
Salphro	0.5	11.29 (46.86)	0.4686	1717.45	-
	1.0	9.99 (52.89)	0.5289	1410.40	-
	2.0	7.95 (62.51)	0.6251	1049.34	-
	4.0	5.21 (75.37)	0.7537	793.23	20.30
	8.0	3.37 (84.11)	0.8411	516.06	21.62
Salphben	0.5	2.38 (88.79)	0.8877	376.98	-
	1.0	2.12 (90.0)	0.90	318.69	-
	2.0	1.40 (93.40)	0.9340	213.71	-
	4.0	0.97 (96.88)	0.9688	147.82	22.60
	8.0	0.69 (96.85)	0.9685	106.42	24.42

crease in weight loss with increase in inhibitor concentration thus the inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration of the inhibitors. This attributed to an

stand the mechanism of inhibition. Table 2 shows the effect of inhibitors on the corrosion characteristics of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ containing 8 mM concentration of the

Table 2. Effect of inhibitors on the corrosion characteristics of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ containing 8 mM additive (duration : 1 h)

Temp./ parameters	Additive		
	Salphac	Salphro	Salphben
Temp. 30 °C :			
Wt. loss (mg/dm ² /h)	4.49	3.37	0.69
% Inhibition	78.83	84.11	96.88
Surface coverage (θ)	0.7883	0.8411	0.9688
Corrosion rate (mpy)	689.98	516.06	106.42
ΔG (kJ/mol)	18.74	23.98	26.86
Temp. 40 °C :			
Wt. loss (mg/dm ² /h)	7.80	5.40	0.79
% Inhibition	63.22	74.54	96.22
Surface coverage (θ)	0.6322	0.7454	0.9622
Corrosion rate (mpy)	3574.71	987.03	365.64
ΔG (kJ/mol)	13.27	14.32	20.16
Temp. 60 °C :			
Wt. loss (mg/dm ² /h)	12.52	7.98	1.10
% Inhibition	40.97	62.37	94.81
Surface coverage (θ)	0.4097	0.6237	0.9481
Corrosion rate (mpy)	6649.3	3649.6	505.52
ΔG (kJ/mol)	14.06	18.65	24.16
Temp. 80 °C :			
Wt. loss (mg/dm ² /h)	17.09	11.85	1.52
% Inhibition	24.14	55.38	92.84
Surface coverage (θ)	0.2414	0.5538	0.9284
Corrosion rate (mpy)	10238.82	9594.2	662.89
ΔG (kJ/mol)	11.48	12.27	19.74

additives. The effect of temperature (30–80 °C) on the corrosion inhibition with and without inhibitors are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the weight loss increases with temperature in the absence and presence of inhibitors. Adsorption and desorption of inhibitor molecules continuously occur at the metal surface and an equilibrium exists between two process at a particular temperature. With the increase of temperature, the equilibrium between adsorption and desorption processes is shifted leading to a higher desorption rate than adsorption until equilibrium is again established at a different value of equilibrium constant. It explains the lower inhibition efficiency at higher temperature²⁹. Decrease in power to protect with increase in the temperature clearly establishes acceleration in corrosion rate and weakening of bonding forces between the metal surface and the inhibitors³⁰. At elevated temperature the metal surface remains uncovered for longer duration resulting in decrease in corrosion^{31,32}.

The thermodynamic parameters were calculated as done earlier³³. The values of activation energies were calculated from the slopes of Arrhenius plots and are recorded in Table 1. E_a values are higher in presence of inhibitor and it increases with increase in inhibitor concentration. The adsorption of inhibitor molecules causes an increase in the activation energy of the process and the extent is proportional to the extent of adsorption³⁴. Higher activation energy in presence of inhibitor is bound to the surface by specific adsorption process^{35,36}.

The nature of inhibitor interaction on the metal surface during corrosion inhibition of metals and alloys has been deduced from adsorption characteristic of the inhibitor³⁷. The surface coverage (θ) is very useful while discussing the adsorption phenomena and is calculated as done earlier³⁸. To examine the adsorption behaviour of the inhibitor, the data has been fitted to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm giving a straight line supporting the monolayer adsorption of the inhibitors on the metal surface³⁹.

The values of ΔG are recorded in Table 2. The negative values of free energy of adsorption show strong interaction of inhibitor molecules⁴⁰ and spontaneous adsorption on the metal surface⁴¹ with high adsorption efficiency⁴².

Polarization studies :

The potentiodynamic polarization data derived from the plots have been given in Table 3. The values of current density (I_{corrs}) were obtained from Tafels slopes to the corrosion potential (E_{corrs}). The percentage inhibition obtained by polarization measurements are in good agreement with that obtained from weight loss measurements and increases with the increase in inhibitor concentration as found in the case of weight loss studies. The shift in both b_a and b_c without any appreciable change in E_{corrs} , the inhibitors used may be classified as mixed inhibitors retarding both anodic and cathodic reactions.

Mechanism of inhibition :

Organic molecules known to inhibit corrosion by an adsorption mechanism^{43–47}. The effectiveness of a compound as a corrosion inhibitor depends on the structure of organic compound⁴⁸. The inhibition of corrosion caused by the condensation products can be due to interactions between π-electron of benzene ring and the lone pair of electrons present on N- and S-hetro atoms, with the positively charged metal surface. Presence of azomethine (>C=N) group also plays a major role in increasing the

Table 3. Polarization parameters of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ at 30±1 °C containing different concentrations of inhibitors

Sl. no.	Parameters	Blank	Inhibitors (mM)								
			Salphac			Salphro			Salphben		
			0.5	4.0	8.0	0.5	4.0	8.0	0.5	4.0	8.0
1.	OCP (-mV)	400	485	492	48	558.8	540.2	536.8	518.0	502.8	508.5
2.	<i>b_a</i> (mV/dec)	74.21	52.61	74.12	55.54	38.02	40.16	45.86	64.8	61.86	65.62
3.	<i>b_c</i> (mV/dec)	128.16	117.83	157.0	112.2	90.65	84.68	48.28	125.19	123.92	119.56
4.	<i>E_{corr}</i> (-mV)	440.00	446.5	452.8	456.1	539.8	530.6	534.12	518.6	514.3	512.84
5.	<i>I_{corr}</i> (μA/cm ²)	1594.6	625.8	540.0	150.2	308.6	87.16	72.46	92.80	84.9	14.6
6.	Percentage inhibition	-	54.48	59.86	90.55	80.69	94.53	95.37	87.99	94.61	97.82

inhibition performance mainly depends on the type and nature of the substituents present in the inhibitor molecule^{53,54}. From the comparison of results of the work it has been concluded by the authors that the π -electron interaction between adsorbed molecules and the metal surface has a characteristic influence on the adsorption behaviour of organic substances⁵⁵.

The adsorption mechanism of Schiff bases has been discussed by some early investigators. The inhibition action of these compounds has been attributed to the strong adsorption of these molecules with metal through -OH, >C=N and -OCH₃^{19,56}. The FTIR studies have confirmed the formation of polymeric complex on metal surfaces⁵⁷. Recent investigation by using FTIR spectral studies of pure Schiff bases and the protective film formed on the metal surface have suggested that the shifting of -CH=N-stretching frequency from 1605 cm⁻¹ (pure base) to 1583 cm⁻¹ (protective film) is due the shifting of electron density towards Fe^{II} resulting in co-ordination between nitrogen atom and Fe^{II}²⁸. The shift of IR group frequencies are also expected to have involved in the co-ordination bond formation with the metal surface has also been concluded²⁸.

Hence, the adsorption mechanism has been suggested for the corrosion inhibition of all the three Schiff bases used in the present investigation. They have expected to have adsorbed on the metal surface by (i) electrostatic interaction between the inhibitor and the metal surface, (ii)

the unshared electron pair on nitrogen atoms interact with metal surface due to the flat orientation of the entire molecule and (iii) the interaction of π -electrons of aromatic ring as well as -CH=N- group with the metal surface.

Mechanism of effect of substitution on inhibition :

The variation in inhibition performance mainly depends on the type and nature of the substituents present in the inhibitor molecule. The inhibition efficiency values obtained by various methods are given in the Tables 1, 2 and 3 indicate that inhibition efficiency values of the three inhibitors tested follow the order :

The effectiveness of a compound as a corrosion inhibitor depends on the structure of organic compound⁴⁸. The groups with +I effect on azomethine carbon, generally have a tendency to increase the π -electron interaction. As the number of group with +I effect on >C=N-increases, the π -electron density on the azomethine carbon increases favouring greater adsorption of the inhibitors. Hence, -CH₃ group in Salphro is expected to adsorb to a greater extent than Salphac resulting more inhibition. The reason for Salphben giving enhanced inhibition efficiency than Salphro may be due to the greater adsorbability of the additional phenyl group on the metal surface by its flat orientation and also provides additional anchoring sites for adsorption on the metal surface through the π -electron cloud. These extensively delocalized π -electrons favour greater adsorption on the metal surface⁵⁸.

Conclusion :

Corrosion inhibition is attributed to adsorption of the inhibitors on the mild steel following Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration of the additives. The lone pair of electron of nitrogen atom along with the delocalized π -electrons can be attributed for higher inhibition efficiency. Thermodynamic parameter (E_a) indicates that the adsorption of inhibitor molecules cause an increase in activation energy. The negative values of free energy of adsorption show strong interaction of the inhibitors and spontaneous adsorption on the metal surface. All the Schiff bases act as mixed inhibitors retarding both anodic and cathodic reactions follow the inhibition order :

Experimental

All the Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of two mole equivalents of salicylaldehyde, phenylenediamine and respective aldehyde or ketone by following the reported procedure⁵⁹. All the reagents used were chemically pure grade. The standard procedures⁶⁰ were used to purify and drying the solvents. The metal specimens, their preparation, the methods of measuring the corrosion rate, potential, percentage inhibition and polarization were the same as described earlier³³.

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